

Transcription system for deaf people

Sistema de transcrição para pessoas com deficiência auditiva
Sistema de transcripción para personas con discapacidad auditiva

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Abstract:

The main objective of this paper is to develop an Internet of Things (IoT) system that aids communication between deaf and hearing people, especially in academic and professional contexts. The project consists of a portable microcomputer with a touch screen and omnidirectional microphone, capable of voice recognition, in conjunction with a mobile application, for customization of the portable device and transcription management. The qualitative methodology was employed to identify the problems faced by deaf people, which highlighted the difficulties of social interaction and the lack of access to quality education and honest work. It is expected that Sonoris will reduce barriers in places that lack accessibility for these individuals, thereby increasing autonomy, opportunities, and dignity for all.

Keywords: *Accessible Technology; Inclusive Communication; Hearing Impairment; Voice Recognition.*

Resumo:

Este trabalho tem como objetivo principal desenvolver um sistema baseado nos conceitos de Internet das Coisas (IoT) para auxiliar pessoas com deficiência auditiva a interagir com ouvintes em ambientes acadêmicos e profissionais. Ele consiste em um dispositivo portátil que contém um microcomputador e um microfone omnidirecional, capaz de captar a fala humana e transcrevê-la em uma tela touch que conta com um aplicativo mobile para sua configuração do dispositivo e gerenciamento das transcrições captadas. Foi utilizada a metodologia qualitativa para identificar os problemas enfrentados pelas pessoas com deficiência auditiva, o que evidenciou a dificuldade de interação desses indivíduos com a sociedade e a falta de ensino de qualidade e trabalho justo. Espera-se que a Sonoris reduza as barreiras comunicativas em locais sem acessibilidade, resultando em mais autonomia, oportunidades e dignidade para todos.

Palavras-chave: *Tecnologia Acessível; Comunicação Inclusiva; Deficiência Auditiva; Reconhecimento de Voz.*

Resumen:

El objetivo principal de este trabajo es desarrollar un sistema basado en conceptos de la Internet de las Cosas (IoT) para ayudar a las personas con discapacidad auditiva

a interactuar con sus oyentes en entornos académicos y profesionales. Consiste en un dispositivo portátil con una microcomputadora y un micrófono omnidireccional, capaz de capturar el habla humana y transcribirla a una pantalla táctil. También incluye una aplicación móvil para configurar el dispositivo y gestionar las transcripciones capturadas. Se empleó una metodología cualitativa para identificar los problemas que enfrentan las personas con discapacidad auditiva, destacando las dificultades que enfrentan para interactuar con la sociedad y la falta de educación de calidad y empleo justo. Se espera que Sonoris reduzca las barreras de comunicación en entornos inaccesibles, lo que se traduce en mayor autonomía, oportunidades y dignidad para todos.

Palabras clave: *Tecnología accesible; Comunicación inclusiva; Discapacidad auditiva; Reconocimiento de voz.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Until the 20th century, deaf people were frequently seen as incapable of performing any work in society, owing to certain limitations or difficulties caused by their auditory condition, as reported by UFMG (2022). Currently, deaf people still encounter communication obstacles that affect their inclusion and acceptance in society, resulting in a sense of exclusion, according to Magno (2021).

One of the biggest difficulties faced by deaf people is the lack of knowledge of Brazilian Sign Language (Libras) among a significant portion of the hearing and deaf population, as stated by Silva, Hora, and Carvalho (2019). Also pertinent to the problem is the lack of inclusive education resources for these individuals, such as interpreters in lectures and classes, which can make it more difficult for them to access quality education and consequently enter the job market.

Hence, the project Sonoris was developed to help deaf people communicate, contributing to their inclusion, particularly in educational and professional contexts where effective communication is most important. With this in mind, a mobile application was created using the Flutter framework, and a portable device was developed in Python, offering an intuitive and pleasant experience that allows the user to easily interact with the system.

In this context, Sonoris is an assistive technology (AT), a growing field essential to the participation and inclusion of people with disabilities across various social contexts, as Rodrigues and Alves (2013) point out.

With that in mind, how can assistive technology help reduce the social barriers deaf people face when communicating with hearing people?

2. THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

This topic will explore the primary technologies and theoretical foundations employed in the documentation and development of the Sonoris project.

2.1 Hearing Impairment and Deafness

According to Article 1 of Law No. 14,768, of December 22, 2023 (our translation):

Article 1 – A hearing impairment is considered a long-term limitation of hearing, either total unilateral or partial or total bilateral, which, in interaction with one or more barriers, hinders the full and effective participation of the person in society on an equal basis with others. (BRAZIL, 2023, our translation)

As highlighted by a survey conducted by the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (2012), about 4.6% of the population — about 9 million Brazilians — suffer from some type of hearing impairment, and about 1% suffer from profound deafness.

2.2 Internet of Things (IoT)

In the words of Magrani (2018) the Internet of Things is a concept in which

distinct physical devices interact with each other through sensors and objects to create practical solutions for everyday life. It is not just about the representation of connecting devices through the smartphone, but about making these devices smart, capable of capturing and analyzing data from the environment or networks to which it is connected, as emphasized by Oliveira (2017).

As Santos (2019) stated, IoT can automate everyday tasks without human intervention.

2.3 Raspberry Pi

According to Eberman et al. (2017), in 2006, Eben Upton, Rob Mullins, Jack Lang, and Alan Mycroft proposed creating an accessible microcomputer called the Raspberry Pi to teach young people about programming logic. However, the success of this module and its high processing power showed that it could be used in other scenarios, especially in embedded systems, as stated by Oliveira (2017).

Thus, the Raspberry Pi 3 Model B was used for this project, since, according to RoboCore (2025), it has important features, such as Wi-Fi, Bluetooth Low Energy, and multiple USB ports for peripherals, which are crucial for the development of Sonoris.

Figure 1 - Raspberry Pi 3B

Source: Own Authorship (2025)

2.4 Python

Donat (2018) notes that the creators of the Raspberry Pi chose Python because it was considered an efficient, simple, and easy-to-learn language. In addition to its ease of use, this language also features essential components, such as PIP (Package Installer for Python), which is presented in the official Python packaging documentation (2024) as the standard tool for installing Python packages. This allows developers to find and add libraries in the terminal easily.

2.5 Flutter

As stated by Alura (2022), Flutter is a framework that utilizes the Dart Programming language and aims to facilitate the development of mobile applications for various operating systems.

Bitencourt (2022) highlights that Dart is an object-oriented language that integrates programming principles and supports reactive programming, which responds to data changes, thus increasing its flexibility for developing various applications.

Additionally, Dart uses AOT (Ahead-of-Time) and JIT (Just-in-Time) compilation, which compile code before execution, resulting in greater stability and faster startup and component updates, as Marinho (2020) points out.

2.6 Firebase

According to Bernardino and Barros (2025), Firebase is a platform on Google Cloud that facilitates and accelerates application development by providing cloud synchronization services.

Cloud Firestore, from Firebase, is a NoSQL database that stores and synchronizes data in real time, even when offline, and provides high performance and scalability for queries, in line with Rodrigues (2021) perspective.

2.7 Unified Modeling Language (UML)

Guedes (2018) claims that the Unified Modeling Language is a versatile, illustrative modeling language, widely used to design the structure of object-oriented software. It is essential because it helps understand the applications and their functionalities, as well as document their entire trajectory and the processes used to complete them, as stated by Booch, Rumbaugh, and Jacobson (2012).

As Fowler (2005) highlighted, UML was created by unifying modeling languages from the 1990s, facilitating the development of diagrams and documentation. Below is an example of a use case diagram:

Figure 2 – Example of a use case diagram

Source: Own Authorship (2024)

The figure above represents the use case diagram of a veterinary clinic system, where we have, in total, three fundamental actors, namely:

The “pet guardian”, who represents the veterinary clinic’s client, can register an account in the system, manage their appointments, register their pets, and finally manage their adoption listings.

The “employee”, responsible for submitting appointment reports after the appointment is completed, registering other employees and verifying adoption announcements to ensure their authenticity;

Finally, the “administrator”, whose sole function is to manage the application’s database tables, ensuring easy and quick maintenance. Likewise, they have the same functions as an employee, just as an employee performs the same functions as the pet’s guardian.

Besides, many of these interactions performed by the actors require login before execution, represented by the <<include>> relationship, which means that one use case is linked to another.

2.8 3D printing

According to Lor (2018), 3D modeling can simulate environments and materials in a given scene, allowing an artificially created object to be physically replicated.

Furthermore, according to Aguiar (2006), 3D printing is a technique for building solids previously modeled in 3D by depositing layers, unlike other methods that sculpt the material until the desired shape is formed.

3. METHOD

Throughout this chapter, we will discuss the steps taken in the conception, documentation, and development of the project, based on the concepts demonstrated in the authors' theoretical foundation.

3.1 Development Methodology

For the theoretical foundation, a qualitative methodology was used to consolidate Sonoris. This approach focuses on understanding social phenomena and on valuing human experiences rather than data and statistics. It allowed for an accurate understanding of the target audience's experiences and perceptions, contributing to the project's improvement.

3.2 System Documentation

Before starting the coding phase of Sonoris, a requirements analysis was conducted to define and document all the system's functionalities, using UML diagrams as a basis.

Business rules (BR) are the conditions and characteristics that differentiate the company from competitors in the market. At the same time, functional requirements (FR) specify the system's capabilities and actions. Finally, non-functional requirements (NFR) are the characteristics that describe how the system should function and the conditions under which it should operate.

Business rules (BR):

- BR01 – The device can only transcribe human speech up to 3 meters away.
- BR02 – Both the IoT and the App must be in pairing mode to be paired.
- BR03 – The device only works when paired with the official app.
- BR04 – The device only works when the user is logged into their account.
- BR05 – Each email address must be unique and cannot be associated with more than one account
- BR06 – The password must be at least 8 (eight) characters long, containing at least one uppercase letter, one lowercase letter and one number.

Application Functional Requirements (FR):

- FR01 – Register account.
- FR02 – Log in.
- FR03 – Pair device.
- FR04 – Manage conversations.
- FR05 – Edit account.
- FR06 – Adjust device preferences.
- FR07 – Manage quick replies.
- FR08 – Play quick replies.

Non-Functional Requirements (NFR):

- NFR01 – The app must be compatible with Android.
- NFR02 – The app must use accessible fonts.
- NFR03 – The system must have a user-friendly interface.
- NFR04 – It must be possible to securely save conversations.
- NFR05 – The system must guarantee the device's stability and partial offline functionality.
- NFR06 – The device must have a short response time for detecting human speech.

Below is the system's use case diagram, which illustrates all the interactions between the actor – the one interacting with the application – and their respective use cases – the functionalities provided by the system.

Figure 3 – Sonoris use case diagram

Source: Own Authorship (2025)

The use case diagram above illustrates how the Sonoris system assists deaf people. The actor “deaf person” represents the project’s target audience, which consists of deaf people. This actor has several functionalities within the system, including: registering an account in the application, managing conversations, editing their account, adjusting desired device preferences, managing quick replies according to their tastes, managing quick reply categories, and replaying replies. Most of these interactions require the actor to have logged in or paired the device beforehand.

3.3 Project Visual Identity

A brand's visual identity is fundamental for its recognition by the target audience and for its formal establishment in the market. What defines it are the combinations of logo, color palette, and typography, which convey the necessary emotions to the people who use the application.

The name of this project, Sonoris, was carefully chosen to be easy to identify and memorable for people, as it refers to the word “sonorous”, which means that which produces sound.

Below is the logo, which depicts a white cat with blue eyes, which have about an 80% chance of being born deaf, as a visual representation of Sonoris.

Figure 4 - Sonoris logo

Source: Own Authorship (2025)

The shades of blue, moreover to faithfully representing the blue-eyed cat, also convey to users a sense of stability, loyalty, protection, and commitment.

Regarding typography, Rubik is used for titles, subtitles, and important text that requires emphasis, while Source Sans Pro is used for the rest of the application.

Below are high-fidelity wireframes of the welcome page and the main screen of the IoT device. Both clearly show how the visual components that make up Sonoris' visual identity are represented in the screen layout in a simple, practical, and inviting way for the user.

Figure 5 – Wireframe of the welcome page and the device’s main screen

Source: Own Authorship (2025)

4. RESULTS E DISCUSSIONS

The results obtained with the development of Sonoris contribute to the social inclusion of deaf people, using the Figma design tool for prototyping the application pages, employing user experience (UX) and user interface (UI) methodologies to make the pages more interactive and visually appealing to users, beyond that to Fusion 360, used to model the device case to protect the system hardware.

4.1 Sonoris Application

The application screens were illustrated consistently to strengthen Sonoris's visual identity and facilitate user navigation across the app's pages. To achieve this, the blue tones from the logo were applied to the app's visual elements, such as buttons, titles, and forms, highlighting them and maintaining aesthetic consistency.

In total, the developed mobile application contains 17 screens, using Flutter and Dart as the main technologies. These technologies permit reusable components such as buttons, text fields, color and font variables, and native integration with Firebase, resulting in faster, more consistent development. Below are some screenshots of the created application:

Figure 1 - Screenshot of the loading screen and main screen

Source: Own Authorship (2025)

The first screens of the application are shown above, starting with the loading screen, which appears during initialization and displays the Sonoris logo on a dark blue background. After that, if the user is logged in, they are redirected to the main page, which shows the device status — disconnected at the time of the screenshot — along with quick actions to make navigation easier and a section for the most recent unsaved conversations for quick access. This is also the first screen that includes the navigation bar, which provides access to other important pages of the application, such as the main page, saved conversations page, device page, and user profile page.

Figure 2 – Screenshot of the saved conversations screen and chat screen

Source: Own Authorship (2025)

The screens related to saved conversations can be accessed by clicking Saved in the navigation bar. Starting with the saved conversations screen itself, it offers options that make organizing conversations easier, such as the ability to search and filter them simultaneously. When clicking a conversation, which displays important information such as date, time, and a customized name and description, the user is redirected to a full-page view that shows the entire transcription, with options to edit, delete, or mark it as a favorite.

Figure 8 - Screenshot of the customization captions screen and quick replies screen

Source: Own Authorship (2025)

Other important features of the Sonoris system include the option to customize subtitles, allowing the user to edit colors, font, size, and font weight, as well as the quick answers playback feature, which plays preconfigured answers via text-to-speech when selected.

4.2 Sonoris Device

The device screens were developed in the same way as the application, always following UX and UI principles and maintaining Sonori's brand visual identity, even on a small screen. All screens were created using Python libraries, primarily Kivy, which lets easy interface creation and provides the necessary tools for customization. Below is a screenshot of the device's main screen:

Figure 9 - Screenshot of the device's main screen

Source: Own Authorship (2025)

This is the device's main interface, where captured speech is displayed. It also displays the history of previous dialogues. It includes a toolbar with options to pause, allowing the user to start a new conversation, for instance, and to activate private mode, consequently preventing conversations from being saved and providing greater privacy.

Figure 10 – Screenshot of the customized device's main screen

Source: Own Authorship (2025)

It is important to highlight that user customizations within the app are reflected on this screen, making the device more accessible to everyone.

Since the device is based on the Raspberry Pi 3B microcomputer, it was necessary to design a case that kept the circuit safe and create a more pleasing appearance aligned with the rest of the project, as seen in the following figure:

Figure 3 - Sonoris case design

Source: Own Authorship (2025)

The case design is divided into two parts: the main compartment, painted blue, which secures the Raspberry Pi in place and provides access to the necessary project ports; and the bottom, where ventilation holes are visible and the Sonoris logo is located. Moreover, the second part, painted white and the case lid, secures the compartment, leaving only the screen exposed, with a snap-fit mechanism.

Figure 4 - Visual representation of the Sonoris device.

Source: Own Authorship (2025)

5. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The project seeks to assist in the autonomy of deaf people, to facilitate communication with listeners, especially in the professional and academic sphere, as the device is designed to capture human speech within a wide area around it and save transcripts to the app automatically, which provides an intuitive and enjoyable experience, empowering the users to participate in day-to-day activities actively.

Even if the project has achieved good results, addressing a social problem innovatively and practically, certain functionalities of it can still be improved, such as the more accurate local transcriptions, or even the option to use a transcription through artificial intelligence.

In conclusion, Sonoris is consolidated not only as a system composed of hardware and software, but also as a tool that promotes inclusion and autonomy. It is expected that Sonoris will reduce communication barriers in places lacking accessibility, resulting in more autonomy, opportunities, and dignity for all.

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